

VI International Forum on Teacher Education

Pedagogical Prevention Technology of Extremism Manifestations in Youths Based on Social Competencies

Tatyana V. Romanova* (a)

*Chuvash I. Yakovlev State Pedagogical University, 42800 Cheboksary (Russia), 38, Karl Marx Street,
romashechca77@mail.ru*

Abstract

The relevance of the study is due to the need for a comprehensive scientific study of the nature, specificity and practical methods of organizing pedagogical prevention of manifestations of extremism in the youth environment based on a technological approach. The purpose of this study is to develop pedagogical technology for the prevention of extremism among youth on the basis of social competencies, its experimental justification.

The analysis of literary sources devoted to the study of the problem of the manifestation of extremism in the youth environment made it possible to determine that extremism as a social phenomenon is a destructive behavior of a person, manifested by aggression and violence towards another person.

The study provides examples educational of situations that can be used as the main method in pedagogical technology for the prevention of manifestations of extremism in the youth environment. It has been experimentally proved its effectiveness, using the example of the activity of the psychological and pedagogical faculty of the Chuvash I. Yakovlev State Pedagogical University. The experiment involved 60 people, 2nd year students (30 - EG, 30 - CG).

As a result of introducing the technology of pedagogical prevention of extremism manifestations among youth into the educational process, significant changes were revealed in the experimental group that participated in the formative experiment, in the control group the changes were insignificant. The proposed technology can be used by educational institutions in the process of organizing work to prevent manifestations of extremism in the youth environment.

Keywords: extremism, forms of manifestation of extremism, technology, pedagogical prevention, youth environment, social competencies.

© 2020 Tatyana V. Romanova

This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (CC BY 4.0), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

Published by Kazan federal university and peer-reviewed under responsibility of IFTE-2020 (VI International Forum on Teacher Education)

* Corresponding author. E-mail: romashechca77@mail.ru

Introduction

The problem of preventive prevention of manifestations of extremism among young people arises most acutely not only from the state, but also requires special attention and the adoption of specific preventive measures in the education system. Young people most often commit extremist actions because of ignorance of the consequences of such actions; they need knowledge of the laws and responsibility for the manifestation of extremism. Also, in many cases, young people fall under extremist influences due to their inability to resist negative influences, falling into various associative groups.

In the framework of the implementation of the state program of the Chuvash Republic “Improving the safety of life of the population and territories of the Chuvash Republic” for 2019-2035, which includes the subprogram “Prevention of terrorism and extremist activity in the Chuvash Republic”, a system of measures is being implemented in educational institutions to prevent extremism and terrorism, and form a tolerant consciousness of young people.

This problem of organizing preventive prevention of manifestations of extremism in the youth environment has become the most acute in our Chuvash I. Yakovlev State Pedagogical University with the advent of a large number of foreign students. At this time, 568 foreign students study at the university in full-time and part-time studies. Among them are representatives of Turkmenistan - 549 people, Tajikistan - 2 students, Uzbekistan - 5 people, Ukraine - 1 part-time student, Moldova - 1 student, Kazakhstan - 1 student, China - 9 students. The total percentage of foreign students is about 10%. Therefore, one of the priority areas of educational work in the Chuvash I. Yakovlev State Pedagogical University is - work to prevent manifestations of extremism in the student community.

Purpose and objectives of the study

The aim of our study is to develop a technology for the pedagogical prevention of manifestations of extremism among young people on the basis of the formation of social competencies of a person that can withstand the negative influences of society, its experimental justification.

Literature review

To date, a huge body of information has been accumulated in the theory and practice of psychological and pedagogical research, revealing the scientific foundations and experience in preventing the manifestations

of extremism among young people and adolescents. Studies have shown that many social scientists are actively interested in the problem of youth.

One group of researchers, considering the features of the manifestation of extremism in the behavior of people and society, identifies several approaches for which there are various reasons for this behavior. These include: a biologizing approach; psychoanalytic concepts of sociopathy, where extremism is considered as a form of deviant behavior; sociological concepts explain the causes of extremism as unfavorable social conditions for the existence of people; socio-psychological concepts distinguish extremism as a definite result of interpersonal interaction of a person and her immediate environment.

Another group of researchers considers extremism from a pedagogical point of view, given its sociocultural nature.

Features of the study of the problem of personality formation in the activities of youth associations were considered: Basov (2009), Eroshenkov (2009) and Mogalyuk (2001) and other domestic teachers revealed the problem of organizing teenage and youth public associations.

The study of the socialization of youth in modern conditions was carried out by Kromin (2007), Nyagin (2020), Afanasyeva (2007) and Basov (2009). Value orientations of the young generation: Andreeva (2000) and Bocharova (1994). The problem of international extremism is revealed in many works of foreign researchers as Beck (2009) and Daniker (1995).

Vasilenko (2004) and Fridinsky (2011) address issues of legal solution to the problem of the emergence of organizations of extremist orientation. The essence of the concept of extremism is reflected in the works of domestic scientists: Budnitsky (2000), Dobaev and Nemchina (2005) Lazarev (2017) and Romanova and Petrova (2018).

A significant contribution to the disclosure of the essence of extremism from the point of view of political, legal, economic and sociocultural foundations was made by modern researchers as Baal (2012) and Buzykina (2013). The problem of manifestations of ethno-national, ethno-confessional extremism in Russia and other countries are considered in the works of Chuprov and Zubok (2009), Golovin and Aristakhova (2013), Romanova (2018).

Golovin and Aristarkhova (2013), Chuprov and Zubok (2009) and Vasenina (2007) study the causes of the growth of extremism in the youth environment.

For our study, the most interesting are the works reflecting various aspects of the prevention of deviant youth behavior, namely Almazov (1996), Antonyan, Gorshkova, and Zulkarneev,(1999), Belkin (2000), Karpets (1969), Minkovsky (1972) and Tarasova (2008). Among the works revealing the problem of deviant behavior of young people, the reasons for the manifestations of various deviations, the works of Belicheva (1994), Zeigarnik and Bratus (1980), Lichko (1983), Ratinov, Kroz, and Ratinova (2005). In whose writings it is analyzed that the youth environment, taking into account its social characteristics, is that part of society in which the accumulation and realization of negative protest potential occurs most quickly.

Many researchers highlight the sociocultural component in the formation of the legal personality. In his dissertation research Kuzmin highlights the sociocultural conditions for the prevention of extremism among young people (2015). Prevention of destruction in the youth environment by means of sociocultural management is reflected in the works of Zharkov (1998), Zharkova (2014) and Olenina (2012). Sviridov in his dissertation study "The socio-cultural activities of universities on the prevention of extremism in the youth environment", reveals the essence and peculiarity of the socio-cultural activities of universities on the prevention extremism manifestations in the youth environment from the point of view of pedagogics, considering its scientific orientation (2014). The socio-philosophical analysis presents in his work Afanasyev "Sociocultural conditions for countering extremism among young people". The paper presents objective and subjective factors of manifestation of aggression and extremism in modern social conditions (2007).

The study of the manifestations of political extremism was carried out by Eremin (2015). The sociological approach is reflected in the work of Lazarev, where youth extremism is considered in the conditions of a transforming Russian society (2017).

Zelenov in his dissertation research "Theory and practice of pedagogical prevention of extremist manifestations in the youth environment in the system of continuing professional education", presents a model of pedagogical prevention of extremist manifestations in the youth environment in the system of continuing (secondary and higher) professional education. The basis of the proposed model is to strengthen the role of traditional institutions of socialization, the author emphasizes the importance of the influence of the family and environment on the formation and formation of personality. Emphasizes the need to focus preventive activities on reducing the destructive potential of youth subcultures (2014).

The psychological approach to the problem is reflected in the dissertation research of Buzykin. "Attitudes towards the manifestations of extremism among representatives of various socio-demographic

groups". His work defines the socio-psychological characteristics of extremism. The author identifies the levels of manifestation of extremism, considering the degree of personality exposure to various forms of aggression (2013).

Also in our work, we paid special attention to the consideration of works devoted to the resolution of social problems through the application of social technologies. Features of the application of social technologies in the prevention of deviant behavior are disclosed in the works of Oslon (2016) and Romanova (1994).

After analyzing the scientific research on the problem we are studying, it allowed us to conclude that the researchers pay most attention to the nature of extremism, its genesis, developmental features, the study of its social consequences and its prevention. Nevertheless, most of the research work is political, legal in nature, which required a deeper look at the pedagogical foundations of the prevention of extremism in the youth environment.

Methodology

Experimental work was carried out on the basis of the Chuvash I. Yakovlev State Pedagogical University, at the of psychological and pedagogical faculty. The experiment was attended by 60 2nd year students. Two groups of 30 students each were distinguished, one experimental group and another control group.

An analysis of the available methods of psychological diagnostics showed that to date, there are no "direct" methods for diagnosing an individual's tendency to extremist manifestations in the arsenal of psychodiagnostics, so we took the following methods to determine the level of tendency to manifest extremism, which are according to our observations more reflect the level of extremism among youth:

- a methodology for diagnosing a tendency toward deviant behavior, developed by Orel (Kleyber, 2004) which allows one to determine and measure the degree of readiness for various forms of deviant behavior;
- a technique for diagnosing a degree of risk preparedness, by Schubert. This technique allows you to assess the characteristics of human behavior in a dangerous situation, when violations of established norms and rules are required, which allows you to determine the degree of readiness of a person to risk;
- a questionnaire on the attitude of citizens to manifestations of extremism in modern society, which, according to our observations, more reflects the level of manifestation of extremism among young people;

- a technique for diagnosing the state of aggression (Bass-Darki Questionnaire). This technique allows you to determine the presence of destructive trends, mainly in the field of subject-object relations;
- the technique of “level of correlation of value” and “accessibility” in various life spheres”, by Fantalova (2001). This methodology considers 12 basic universal values and reveals the correlation of such psychological parameters as “Value” (C) and “Accessibility” (D) for a person of each of these values. The main psychometric characteristic of this test is the indicator “Value-Availability” (C-D), which reflects the degree of inconsistency, disintegration in the motivational-personal sphere. The latter, in turn, indicates the degree of dissatisfaction with the current life situation, internal conflict, the blockade of basic needs on the one hand, as well as the level of self-realization, integration, harmony on the other hand.

Experiment description and procedure

As part of our study, a socio-pedagogical experiment was conducted to determine the level of respondents' tendency to manifest extremism and its prevention. To this end, we have chosen a variant of the natural experiment, which was carried out under ordinary conditions for the subjects during the educational process. In the framework of the discipline “Method and technology work of a social educator”.

The social pedagogical experiment was carried out in three stages:

- 1) at the first stage, a stating experiment the carried out, during which we were to identify the tendency of respondents to extremist behavior. The experiment was conducted in the experimental and control groups;
- 2) at the second stage of our study, the developed technology of pedagogical prevention of manifestations of extremism in the youth environment was tested. Currently, there are several approaches to the prevention of manifestations of extremism in the youth environment, in our work we took the approach based on the formation of life skills as a basis. This approach is based on the theory of social learning of Bandura (1969). This approach is aimed at the formation of socially desirable behavior among young people, using social and pedagogical trainings, role-playing games and discussion of situations. The technology developed by us was implemented, introduced into the educational process as part of the discipline "Methodology and Technology of the Social Teacher," with students studying in the profile of "Psychology and Social Pedagogy" in the experimental group;
- 3) at the third stage, a control experiment was conducted, which allowed us to verify the effectiveness of the technology we proposed for the pedagogical prevention of manifestations of extremism in the youth environment. During the experiment, the dynamics of changes in the experimental group were revealed, in

the classroom with which the technology we proposed was implemented. In the control group, indicators remained unchanged.

In the course of a theoretical analysis of studies on the problem we are studying, as well as our practical experience, we have allowed the wound in our studies to come to the conclusion that extremism as a social phenomenon is a destructive behavior of a person, manifested by aggression and violence towards another person.

Among the main characteristics of a person prone to extremism, scientists include the following: a high level of aggression; choice of violent methods and threats; uniformity of perception of social problems, search for ways to solve them; the desire to impose their principles, views on society; unconditional execution of all orders, instructions; inability to empathy, manifestation of tolerance. Among the main psychological characteristics of a person manifesting extremist behavior, the following are distinguished: the desire to act by the most radical means, which is manifested by extreme aggressiveness; not accepting a different opinion than his own; lack of empathy, sympathy; one-sided perception of everything that happens; extremists are characterized by loneliness, a lack of human warmth; all reality in their minds is colored in dark colors; a feeling of superiority over others; high willingness to use violence.

Having examined the various characteristics of a person prone to extremism, we have identified the following indicators of extremism among young people:

- solving their problems by force, showing various forms of deviant behavior;
- the degree of risk propensity, guided by the principle "to achieve the goal, all means are good";
- not the ability to sympathize and empathize;
- motivated aggression, the purpose of which is to cause harm to someone else.
- rejection of someone else's point of view, inability to come to a compromise solution.

The manifestation of extremism in the youth environment, according to Chuprov and Zubok (2009), is one of the forms of deviant personality behavior, in which the behavior model is expressed in adherence to aggression, extreme views and actions that are dangerous for others. Therefore, one of the priority areas in the prevention of extremism in the youth environment should be the formation of its social competencies. The concept of social competence includes the level of socialization of a person, the level of his social activity; moral and legal maturity of the individual; the ability to build a person's relationship with society and himself. A person with formed social competencies is the exact opposite of a person prone to extremism (Zimnyaya, 2003).

Currently, there are several approaches to the prevention of manifestations of extremism in the youth environment, in our work we took the approach based on the formation of life skills as a basis. This approach is based on the theory of social learning of Bandura (1969). This approach is aimed at the formation of socially desirable behavior among young people, using social and pedagogical trainings, role-playing games and discussion of situations.

As the main method in the technology we proposed, we included educative situations. Educative situations can be an effective method of preventing the manifestations of extremism among young people in educational organizations. Nurturing situations are diverse in content and universal in terms of application. The use of educative situations in the technology of pedagogical prevention of manifestations of extremism in the youth environment will allow the formation of basic social competencies, namely:

- 1) the ability to take responsibility for their actions, participate in decision-making, analyze and adjust;
- 2) a value attitude to one's own life, to the life of other people, forming permissible interpersonal interactions;
- 3) the need to comply with social norms;
- 4) knowledge of the causes, development, consequences of extremist behavior and the possibilities of overcoming it.

The use of educative situations in the proposed technology, we divided into four blocks based on the above social competencies.

The first block of situations is aimed at the formation of a social model of behavior. This block involves the inclusion of participants in socially approved activities. Attracting youth to socially approved activities contributes to the formation of an individual model of behavior, an adequate situation, the search for solutions and ways to overcome problems, and the ability to apply theoretical knowledge in specific situations.

The following situations may be included in this block:

1. Game situations. They allow you to lose situations that may arise in real life. For example: "You are being persuaded to do wrong. Your actions?", The analysis of such situations is aimed at developing the ability to defend one's point of view.

2. Situations of translation skills. Participants are encouraged to act out situations by showing possible patterns of behavior.

The second block of educative situations is aimed at creating a culture of a healthy and safe lifestyle. The following situations can be included in this block:

1. Emotional situations. They initiate emotional experiences, both positive and negative. Effective use of the contrast of emotions. For example: a healthy, successful young man and the opposite is oppressed, scared, tortured, etc.

2. Psycho-role situations. Participants are invited to get used to a certain role and feel how a person feels in a particular situation. Also, participants can be invited to tell about themselves in the person of another person, describing their positive and negative sides. Playing this situation will allow you to look at your behavior from the side.

The third block of situations is aimed at creating the need for young people to observe social norms. The block may include the following situations:

1. Situations of reflection. Participants are offered information to reflect on themselves, their behavior, which contributes to their self-development. For example, a situation-discussion on the topic: "Extremism through the eyes of youth", "Healthy lifestyle and youth - are the concepts compatible?"

2. Situations of choice. Participants act as the active subject of the choice of point of view. You can ask a question, a problem: "In life, you need to try everything?" Participants respond: "I completely agree"; "Partially agree"; "I do not agree." After the vote, participants are invited to group in like-minded groups and make compelling statements in favor of their choice. The following is a general discussion of why those in the group support one or another point of view.

The fourth block of situations is aimed at the formation and consolidation of knowledge about the causes and consequences of extremist activity, about ways out of risky situations. This block may include the following situations:

1. The situation of knowledge sharing. In this situation, the participants act as an informant. For example, a press conference or round table on a given problem is organized. One of the participants is offered the role of the leader, which answers the questions of other participants acting as listeners.

2. The situation “Dear editors”, where participants act as journalists, conduct a column and formulate answers to peer questions in writing.

3. The situation of choosing a model of behavior. Participants are offered a set of different cards with the image of the actors and their statements. For example, on each card there are several ways out of the situation. Participants must choose the most suitable, acceptable from their point of view and justify their position.

4. The situation of joint creative activity. Participants are invited to independently create a variety of information materials for the implementation of prevention: booklets, posters, presentations, videos, etc., as well as the development and implementation of preventive materials. So, every year our students participate in the contest of social videos “Youth against extremism”. Participation in such contests forms a rejection of extremism among young people. More than once students took part in the All-Russian youth forum "ETNOVolna" in the city of Glazov. The forum organizers have prepared an educational program for the participants. Students attended lectures on the creation of various ethnic routes. Specialists in this field taught to talk interestingly, fascinatingly about villages, small towns in such a way as to convey the atmosphere to the guests. At the end, the presentation of the results of the laboratory on the development of ethnographic routes and the creation of social videos was presented. The forum participants were representatives of different nationalities. Attracting youth to such events allows not only to consolidate knowledge about the causes and consequences of extremist activity, about ways out of risky situations, but also to instill the ability to work together, listen and respect the opinion of another person. It allows young people to better understand and structure the information received.

During the experiment, students of the experimental group taking part in playing various educational situations acquired: the ability to take responsibility for their actions; value attitude to one’s own life, to the life of other people, forming permissible interpersonal interactions; the need to comply with social norms; knowledge of the consequences of extremist behavior and the possibilities of overcoming it.

Our program is designed for 5 lessons in each block, total 20 lessons lasting 90 minutes, conducted once a week.

Results

At the first stage, of a stating experiment the conducted in which two groups took part. The following results were obtained:

1) according to the methodology for diagnosing a tendency to deviant behavior by Orel (Kleyber, 2004):

The level of attitude towards socially desirable answers: in the EG is high - 33% (10 people), average - 67% (20 people) of respondents; in the CG, high - 37% (11 people), average - 63% (19 people); no low level was detected in both groups.

The propensity to overcome norms and rules: in the EG, high - 20% (6 people), medium - 60% (18 people), low - 20% (6 people) of respondents; in the CG, high - 17% (5 people), average - 57% (17 people), low 33% (10 people) of respondents.

Addictive behavior level: in the EG, high - 20% (6 people), medium - 50% (15 people), low - 30% (9 people) of respondents; in the CG, high - 17% (5 people), average - 53% (16 people), low 37% (11 people) of respondents.

The level of propensity to self-damaging and self-destructive behavior: in the EG is high - 23% (7 people), medium - 60% (18 people), low - 17% (5 people) of respondents; in the CG, high - 20% (6 people), medium - 50% (15 people), low 30% (9 people) of respondents.

The level of propensity to aggression and violence: in the EG, average - 63% (19 people), low - 37% (11 people) of respondents; in the CG, average - 60% (18 people), low 40% (12 people) of respondents.

The level of volitional control of emotional reactions: in the EG, high - 40% (12 people), medium - 37% (11 people), low - 23% (7 people) of respondents; in the CG, high - 43% (13 people), average - 37% (11 people), low 20% (6 people) of respondents.

The tendency to delinquent behavior: in the EG is high - 33% (10 people), medium - 44% (13 people), low - 23% (7 people) of respondents; in the CG, high - 30% (9 people), medium - 47% (14 people), low 23% (7 people) of respondents.

2) according to the method of diagnosing the degree of preparedness for Schubert's risk: medium in the EG - 83% (25 people), low - 17% (5 people); in the CG, average - 86% (26 people), low - 13% (4 people) of respondents. No high level was detected in both groups.

3) based on the results of a survey on the attitude of citizens to manifestations of extremism in modern society: in the EG, 7% (2 people) of respondents showed a positive attitude towards manifestations of extremism. It was not detected in the CG.

4) according to the results of the methodology of Fantalova (2001) "the level of correlation of" value "and" accessibility "in various areas of life." In the EG, a high ratio of "value" and "accessibility" in various life spheres is 7% (2 people); the average in 43% (13 people) and 50% (15 people) – low. In the CG, 0% (0 people) have a high ratio of "value" and "accessibility" in life spheres; average at 50% (15 people) and 50% (15 people) – low;

That is, in the EG and the CG, it is possible for 50% of the respondents, that is, for 15 people, to diagnose inconsistency, disintegration in the motivational-personal sphere, dissatisfaction with the current life situation, the state of internal conflict, the blockade of basic needs, as well as the level of self-realization, integration, harmony.

5) according to the results of the methodology for diagnosing the state of Bass-Darki aggression: in the EG, 37% (11 people) of the respondents had a high level of hostility, 57% (17 people) - medium and 7% (2 people) - low; it also follows from the results of this methodology that 7% (2 people) of respondents have a high level of aggressiveness, 50% (15 people) have an average level and 43% (13 people) have a low level. In the CG, 27% (8 people) of respondents had a high level of hostility, 50% (15 people) had an average level and 23% (7 people) had a low level; it also follows from the results of this methodology that 0% (0 people) of respondents have a high level of aggressiveness, 53% (16 people) have an average level and 47% (14 people) have a low level.

According to the results of a stating experiment in the EG, we identified 2 students (7%) with a positive attitude to the manifestations of extremism. Therefore, in this group, our proposed technology for the prevention of manifestations of extremism in the youth environment was implemented based on the formation of social competencies.

Conducting classes using the technology developed by us has significantly improved the indicators obtained during the ascertaining experiment, which confirms the results of the control stage of the experiment in the control and experimental group. The obtained indicators in the control group remained the same, in the experimental group they improved significantly.

We have obtained the following results (presented in Tables 1-3):

1. According to the diagnostic technique for deviant behavior by Orel (Kleyber, 2004), we compared the following most important indicators in our opinion: a high level of propensity to overcome norms and rules in the EG decreased from 20% (6 people) to 7% (2 people), in the CG the indicator did not change, 16% (5 people) of the respondents remained; a high propensity for addictive behavior in the EG decreased from

20% (6 people) to 3% (1 person), in the CG the indicator changed very slightly from 16% (5 people) to 13% (4 people) of respondents; a high propensity for self-damaging and self-destructive behavior in the EG decreased from 23% (7 people) to 3% (1 person), in the CG the indicator decreased slightly from 20% (6 people) to 16% (5 people) of respondents; after a formative experiment, a low level of volitional control of emotional reactions in the EG was not detected, a high level rose from 40% (12 people) to 53% (16 people); in the CG, the low level remained unchanged 20% (6 people) of respondents; the high propensity for delinquent behavior in the EG decreased from 33% (10 people) to 6% (2 people), the CG indicator did not change, 30% (9 people) of the respondents remained.

Table 1. Dynamics of changes in indicators according to the diagnostic technique for deviant behavior by Orel (Kleyber, 2004) in the EG and CG before and after the experiment (in percent).

Level	EG		CG	
	Before	After	Before	After
Propensity to overcome norms and rules	20	7	16	16
Addiction behavior	20	3	16	13
Propensity for self-harming and self-destructive behavior	23	3	20	16
Of control of emotional reactions	40	53	43	43
Of inclination towards deviant behavior	33	6	30	30

2. According to the methodology for diagnosing Schubert's risk preparedness: in the EG, the average level of risk preparedness in the EG decreased from 83% (25 people) to 63% (19 people), the low level from 17% (5 people) increased up to 37% (11 people) of respondents; in the CG indicators have not changed.

Table 2. Dynamics of changes in indicators according to the method of degree of preparedness for Schubert risk in the EG and CG before and after the experiment (in percent).

Levels	EG		CG	
	Before	After	Before	After
Low	17	37	13	13
Medium	83	63	86	86
High	0	0	0	0

3. According to the results of a survey of respondents with a positive attitude towards extremist manifestations, no.

4. According to the results of the methodology of Fantalova "the level of correlation of" value "and" accessibility "in various areas of life." In the EG, the low ratio of "value" and "accessibility" in various life spheres decreased from 50% (15 people) to 16% (5 people). In the CG, the indicators remained the same (2001).

That is, in the EG, the number of people with a state of internal conflict, dissatisfaction with the current life situation has significantly decreased, which also confirms the effectiveness of the technology we have proposed.

5. According to the results of the methodology for diagnosing the state of Bass-Darki aggression: in the EG, a high level of hostility decreased from 37% (11 people) to 13% (4 people); a high level of aggressiveness in the EG was not detected. There were no changes in the CG.

Table 3. Dynamics of changes in indicators according to the method for diagnosing the state of Bass-Darki aggression in the EG and CG before and after the experiment (in percent)

Levels	EG		CG	
	Before	After	Before	After
Of hostility	37	13	27	0
Of aggressiveness	7	0	0	0

Discussion

At a ascertaining stage of the experiment, it was revealed that young people prone to extremism are characterized by a low level of correlation of "value" and "accessibility" in various life spheres ", a high level of aggression, a tendency to self-damaging and self-destructive behavior, a low level of volitional control of emotional reactions .

As a result of introducing the technology of pedagogical prevention of manifestations of extremism among young people into the educational process based on the formation of social competencies, significant changes were identified in the experimental group that participated in the formative experiment, in the control group the changes were insignificant.

Conclusion

Prevention of manifestations of extremism among young people in modern conditions will be more effective with the inclusion of the educational technology we have proposed in the educational process. The technology of pedagogical prevention of manifestations of extremism includes a set of educational situations aimed at reducing the level of manifestations of extremism among young people, based on the development of their social competencies, instilling skills that contribute to the effective resolution of difficult life situations. The main goal of this activity, in our opinion, is the formation of a stress-resistant personality; with formed social competencies, able to withstand the negative influences of society and consciously make behavioral decisions. To organize more effective pedagogical prevention of manifestations of extremism among young people, it is necessary not only to carry out educational work with students, but also organize advanced training courses for employees of educational institutions in order to increase their professional competencies in the field of preventive activities.

Acknowledgements

This work was carried out in accordance with the Program of the Chuvash Republic "Improving the safety of life of the population and territories of the Chuvash Republic" for 2019-2035, including the subprogram "Prevention of terrorism and extremist activity in the Chuvash Republic" in educational institutions.

References

- Abashina, A. D. (2018). Productive pedagogical technologies for the prevention of extremism and terrorism in the youth environment: methodological aspect. *Academy of Professional Education*, 8, 30-40.
- Afanasyeva, R. M. (2007). *Sociocultural conditions for countering extremism in the youth environment* (PhD Thesis). Moscow: National Research University of Electronic Technology.
- Akunina, Yu. A. (2005). *Socio-cultural conditions for the prevention of extremism in the youth environment* (PhD Thesis). Moscow.
- Almazov, B. N. (1996). *Mental environmental maladaptation of minors*. Sverdlovsk: Ural.
- Andreeva, G. M. (2000). *Psychology of social cognition*. Moscow: MGU.

- Antonyan, Y. M., Gorshkova, I. V., & Zulkarneev, R. M. (1999). *Problems of into-family aggression*. Moscow: Research Institute of the Ministry of internal Affairs of Russia.
- Bandura, A. (1969). *Principles of behavior modification*. London: Holt
- Bocharova, V. G. (1994). *Pedagogy of social work*. Moscow: Buya-Argus.
- Vasilenko, V. I. (2004). The concept and typology of terrorism. *Statutes and Decisions*, 40(5), 46-56.
- Baal, N. B. (2012). *Political extremism of Russian youth and technology to overcome it* (PhD Thesis). Nizhny Novgorod: Nizhny Novgorod State University.
- Basov, N. F. (2009). *Social work with youth*. Moscow: Dashkov i Ko.
- Beck, U. (2009). *World at risk*. Cambridge: Polity.
- Belicheva, S. A. (1994). *Fundamentals of preventive psychology*. Moscow: Social health of Russia.
- Belkin, A. S. (2000). *Basics of age pedagogy*. Moscow: Academy.
- Budnitsky, O. V. (2000). *Terrorism in the Russian liberation movement*. Moscow: Political Encyclopedia Publishing House.
- Buzykina, Yu. S. (2013). *Attitude to the manifestations of extremism among representatives of various socio-demographic groups* (PhD Thesis). Chelyabinsk: Chelyabinsk State University.
- Chuprov, V. I., & Zubok, Yu. A. (2009) *Youth extremism: essence, forms of manifestation, trends*. Moscow: Mysl.
- Dobaev, I. P., & Nemchina, V. I. (2005). *New terrorism in the world and in the South of Russia*. Rosrov-on-Don: Rosizdat.
- Daniker, G. (1995). *The guardian soldier: on the nature and use of future armed forces*. New York: United Nations.
- Eremin, D. N. (2015). *Methods of investigating crimes related to political extremism on the materials of the North Caucasus region* (PhD Thesis). Kaliningrad: Immanuel Kant Baltic Federal University.
- Eroshenkov, I. N. (1994). *Cultural and leisure activities in modern conditions*. Moscow: NGIK.

- Fantalova, E. B. (2001). *Diagnostics and psychotherapy of internal conflict*. Samara: BAHRAR.
- Fridinsky, S. N. (2011). *Counteraction of extremist activity (extremism) in Russia (social, legal and criminological research)* (Doctoral Dissertation). Moscow: Kutafin Moscow State Law University.
- Golovin, A. Yu., & Aristarkhova, T. A. (2013) The essence of extremism and the features of its manifestation in the youth environment. *Economic and legal sciences*, 3, 3-9.
- Karpets, I. I. (1969). *The problem of crime*. Moscow: Legal lit.
- Kleyber, Yu. A. (2004). *Social psychology of deviant behavior: a textbook for universities*. Moscow: University.
- Kromin, A. (2007). Russian youth: problems and solutions. *OBNS*, 6, 25-31.
- Kuzmin, A.V. (2015). *Socio-cultural prevention of extremism in the youth environment*. (PhD Thesis). Tambov: Tambov State University.
- Lazarev, D. A. (2017). *Youth extremism in a transforming Russian society: problems of prevention and counteraction* (PhD Thesis). Krasnodar: Kuban State University.
- Lichko, A. N. (1983). *Psychopathy and accentuation of character in adolescents*. Saint Petersburg: Medicine.
- Minkovsky, G. M. (1972). The subject of criminological prevention of crimes and some problems of its effectiveness. *Questions of combating crime*, 17, 16.
- Mogalyuk, E. M. (2001). *Socio-cultural activities of youth public associations as a factor in personal self-realization* (PhD Dissertation). Moscow: Moscow State Institute of Culture.
- Nyagin, V. V. (2020). *Socio-cultural partnership of universities, government agencies and public organizations for the prevention of extremism among young people* (PhD Thesis). Orel: Orel State University.
- Olenina, G. V. (2012). *Socio-cultural design and promotion of civil initiatives of youth: history, theory, methodology, practice*. Barnaul: AGAKI.

- Oslon, V. N. (2016). Orphan Children in the Educational Space of Russia (Following a Survey on Regional Guarantees of Educational Opportunities and Support for Orphans at all Levels of Education). *Psychological Science and Education, 21*(1), 146-155.
- Ratinov, A. R., Kroz, M. V., & Ratinova, N. A. (2005). *Responsibility for inciting hostility and hatred*. Moscow: Yurlitinform.
- Romanova, T. V. (2018). Prevention of manifestations of extremism and terrorism in the youth environment. *Herald of the National Anti-Terrorism Committee, 1*, 46-51.
- Romanova, T. V., & Petrova, I. N. (2018). The essence and content of the concept of "Extremism" and the pedagogical forms of its prevention in the student community. *Herald of the Chuvash State Pedagogical University I. Yakovleva, 1*, 117-123.
- Romanova, O. L. (1994). *Development of ethnic identity among children and adolescents* (PhD dissertation). Moscow: Moscow State University.
- Sviridov, A. A. (2014). *Socio-cultural activities of universities on the prevention of extremism in the youth environment* (PhD Thesis). Tambov: Tambov State University.
- Tarasova, A. E. (2008). *Legal personality of a citizen. Features of legal personality of minors, in manifestations in civil legal relations*. Moscow: Wolters Kluwer Russia.
- Vasenina, I. (2007). Value orientations of student youth and extremism. *Higher Education in Russia, 11*, 116-119.
- Zelenov, Yu. N. (2014). *The theory and practice of pedagogical prevention of extremist manifestations in the youth environment in the system of continuing professional education* (PhD Thesis). Yekaterinburg: Ural State University.
- Zeigarnik, B. V., & Bratus, B. S. (1980). *Essays on the psychology of abnormal personality development*. Moscow: UN-TA.
- Zharkov, A. D. (1998). *The technology of cultural and leisure activities*. Moscow: MSIC.
- Zharkova, L. S. (2014). The problem of meaning in social and cultural activities. *Bulletin of Moscow State University of Culture and Arts, 6*, 62.

Zimnyaya, I. I. (2003). Key competencies - a new paradigm of the result of education. *Higher education today*, 5, 34-42.